

25th International Congress on Sound and Vibration
8-12 July 2018 HIROSHIMA CALLING

NUMERICAL ACOUSTIC CHARACTERISATION OF A KELVIN CELL STRUCTURE UNDER NORMAL AND GRAZING INCIDENCE

Umberto Iemma¹, Giorgio Palma¹, Henry Rice², Lorenzo Burghignoli¹

¹*Department of Engineering, Roma Tre University,*

²*Department of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, School of Engineering, Trinity College Dublin*
email: umberto.iemma@uniroma3.it

Over the last decade, metamaterials based on periodic structures have been largely studied to deeply control and manipulate an acoustic field, exploiting the exotic acoustic behaviours that can be achieved, such as band gaps, hyperfocusing and noise trapping capabilities. In this class of materials, the acoustic response depends on the geometric characteristics, i.e. shape, size, orientation and arrangements of meta-atoms, rather than on the mechanical properties of the base material. Metabehaviours are thus related to constructive and disruptive interactions between incident and reflected waves within the periodic lattice. The present paper deals with the numerical acoustic characterisation of a Kelvin-cell-based layer under normal and grazing incidence. Due to its intricate periodic structure, the Kelvin cell can exhibit interesting acoustic meta-properties, while its high-porosity lattice makes it a good candidate for aeronautical applications, where weight limitation is urgent. Despite an extensive literature on acoustic metamaterials and periodic structures, limited applications on the aeroacoustic responses of these type of structures have been presented so far. The influence of angle of incidence is key to disclose the enormous potential of acoustic metamaterials in aeroacoustics, and possibly open the path to the analysis of the response in more complex situations such as those of interest to the aeronautics community. Ultimately this could make possible the exploitation of unconventional metabehaviours to mitigate the aviation community noise. In this paper, a numerical parametric analysis of the acoustic response of the Kelvin-cell-based specimen is presented, focusing on the search for transmission band-gaps, directivity pattern modifications and energy absorption.

Keywords: acoustic, metamaterial, aeroacoustic, periodic structure, band gap

1. Introduction

The work presented in this article is part of the EU project AERIALIST, financed within the framework Horizon 2020, which goal is the disclosure of the potential of metamaterials to envisage innovative devices for the mitigation of the civil aviation noise. As preliminary action of the project, a validation of the toolchain prototyping–experiments–numerical simulations has to be performed on a concept able to show acoustic behaviours, typical of metamaterials and periodic structures. Part of the activity focused on the study of a periodic structure based on the skeleton of a Kelvin cell, or Tetrakaidecahedron. In 1887, Lord Kelvin proposed that the tetrakaidecahedron was the best shape for packing equal-sized objects together to fill space with minimal surface area[1]. This characteristic makes the cell suitable to build lightweight structures, and hence attractive for aeronautical applications. In addition a small number of parameters can characterise the cell structure.

The structure studied in this work can be considered, as a skeleton of a Kelvin cell, the edge of the crystalline structure being its only remaining part. The numerical simulations performed are focused on the acoustics of a *tile* of Kelvin cells inserted in a hard-backed cavity in a wall surrounded by quiescent fluid or grazed by a background homogeneous flow. In addition, we looked for possible acoustic band gaps of the periodic structure. Effects of the flow on the band gaps are currently under investigation.

2. Numerical simulations

The elementary cell adopted in the present work is a Kelvin cell of $a = 5 \text{ mm}$, with 1mm width struts. The resulting geometry is a composition of elementary cylinders with 1mm diameter connected each other by spherical junctions. The elementary cell is then replicated in the three dimensions to build a *tile* as can be seen in Fig. 1. Numerical simulations are carried out in the frequency domain, hence the governing equation that holds in the fluid domain for acoustic perturbations - in a barotropic, inviscid and irrotational fluid - is the linearized potential equation

$$-\frac{\rho_0}{c_0^2} i\omega (i\omega\phi + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla\phi) + \nabla \cdot \left(\rho_0 \nabla\phi - \frac{\rho_0}{c_0^2} (i\omega\phi + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla\phi) \mathbf{v} \right) = 0 \quad (1)$$

with ϕ the acoustic velocity potential and \mathbf{v} the background aerodynamic velocity field. In the simulations, the walls of each cell are considered as perfectly rigid from an acoustic point of view, hence the boundary conditions reads

$$\nabla\phi \cdot \nabla\Gamma = 0 \quad (2)$$

where Γ is the boundary of the Kelvin cells structure and other hard wall surfaces if present. All simulations were performed using a commercial Finite Element Method solver, Comsol Multiphysics, and a radiation condition is adopted to truncate the computational domain.

The first set of simulations, called Case A, consists in a reflection problem from a 4x4x2 tile, placed in a hard wall cavity, \mathcal{D}_{kc} , that is as deep as the tile resulting thickness, Fig. 2. In \mathcal{D}_{kc} the fluid surrounding the cells is considered quiescent, while in \mathcal{D}_a , the domain above the cavity, the fluid can be either quiescent or moving at $M = 0.2$. A unitary mass point source p_s is placed in \mathcal{D}_{kc} generating the incident pressure field, and two different positions are considered: in the first case the source is centred with the tile and raised with respect to the floor ($\mathbf{x}_{p_s} = (0 \text{ m}, 0 \text{ m}, 0.03 \text{ m})$), while in the second case it is nearer to the floor and out of the tile projection ($\mathbf{x}_{p_s} = (0.015 \text{ m}, 0 \text{ m}, 0.005 \text{ m})$), Fig. 2.

To assess the effect of the presence of the Kelvin cell structure, we use as reference conditions both a flat wall, *i.e.* \mathcal{D}_{kc} is not present and replaced with a hard floor, and an empty cavity, *i.e.* \mathcal{D}_{kc} is not filled with the Kelvin cell tile. The insertion loss

$$IL(\mathbf{x}) = 20 \log_{10} \frac{|p_{kc}(\mathbf{x})|}{|p_{ref}(\mathbf{x})|} \quad (3)$$

where p_{kc} is the pressure field in presence of the KCs tile in the cavity while p_{ref} is the pressure field resulting from each of the two reference cases, is evaluated on a circle of virtual microphones with radius $r_{mic} = 0.02 \text{ m}$ in the frequency range $c_0/20a < f < c_0/5a$.

The second set of simulations, called Case B, consists in a transmission problem from a 8x8x2 KCs tile in open space, with a unitary mass point source p_s producing the incident field. The fluid is considered quiescent (the moving fluid situation is currently under study and results are not yet available) and the mean insertion loss over the interrogation area \mathcal{S}_{IL}

$$\bar{IL} = \overline{20 \log_{10} \frac{|p_{kc}(\mathbf{x})|}{|p_i(\mathbf{x})|}} \Big|_{\mathcal{S}_{IL}} \quad (4)$$

is adopted to evaluate the presence of transmission band gaps of the structure in the ranges of frequency $c_0/20a < f < c_0/5a$ and $c_0/2a < f < c_0/a$.

Figure 1: Numerical discretization of a subset of the Kelvin cell tile (left) and a 3D printed tile from Trinity College Dublin (right).

Figure 2: Sketch of the numerical setup A. A cavity filled with a tile of Kelvin cells is obtained in a hard flat wall. The domain over the cavity is occupied by quiescent or uniformly moving air.

3. Results

Results from simulations previously illustrated are presented in this section. Figures 4 refer to Case A with quiescent fluid and source placed above the center of the cavity, showing waterfalls of the insertion loss evaluated on the circle of microphones for each of the two reference configurations. Figures 6 are analogous to the previous but the fluid in the domain \mathcal{D}_a is moving at $M = 0.2$. Figures 8 and 10 refer to the simulations carried out with the source positioned closer to the ground and uncentered, for the cases with static and moving fluid respectively. Furthermore for selected frequencies pressure field visualization are proposed in Figs. 5 7 9 11. Waterfall plots highlight that, in the analysed frequency range, the KCs structure is substantially transparent from the acoustic point of view. Despite significant differences arise when comparing the results of the simulations in presence of the KC tile and the flat wall, these almost totally disappear when the comparison is done between the KCs tile and the empty cavity. Nevertheless limited regions of the insertion loss waterfall present notably high values. It is also interesting to note how the presence of flow has more influence on the insertion loss when the source is placed centred above the cavity.

For Case B the frequency behaviour of the average insertion loss is shown, along with pressure field visualizations to clearly show an emerging band gap in the proximity of $\frac{\lambda}{a} = 1$. This is consistent with the theory of periodic structures and phononic crystals.

In all the performed simulations thermoviscous losses are not taken into account. However, due to the narrow dimension of the regions inside the periodic structure, *e.g.* between the walls of the

Figure 3: Sketch of the numerical setup B. A tile of Kelvin cells impinged by the incident field from a mass point source. The fluid surrounding the Kelvin cells is quiescent.

Kelvin cells, the effect of viscosity could be non negligible and substantially affect the behaviour of the structure.

Figure 4: Case A - Insertion loss waterfall, $M = 0.0$, $\mathbf{x}_{ps} = (0\text{ m}, 0\text{ m}, 0.03\text{ m})$, comparison with flat wall (left) and empty cavity (right).

4. Conclusions

Acoustic simulations showed minimal influence from the presence inside the cavity of considered Kelvin cell in the studied frequency range. The insertion loss analysis showed a band gap at a wavelength comparable with the characteristic length of the crystalline structure, compatibly with a phononic crystal-like behaviour. Deeper investigation is needed to unveil the real acoustic potential of this structure. In particular, cells with different characteristic length should be studied in future simulations, also considering thermoviscous losses to correctly capture the physical phenomenon that are involved in the narrow regions inside the periodic structure itself, especially for cells of reduced size. Due to its geometrical complexity, direct simulation of the proposed structure is extremely time and resource expensive (even for lossless acoustics), hence a reduced / semi-empirical modelling approach is under development as a next step in the project.

Figure 5: Case A - pressure field visualization $f = 4053\text{Hz}$, $M = 0.0$, $\mathbf{x}_{p_s} = (0\text{ m}, 0\text{ m}, 0.03\text{ m})$, flat wall (left) cavity with Kelvin cells (center) and empty cavity (right).

Figure 6: Case A - Insertion loss waterfall, $M = 0.2$, $\mathbf{x}_{p_s} = (0\text{ m}, 0\text{ m}, 0.03\text{ m})$, comparison with flat wall (left) and empty cavity (right).

Figure 7: Case A - pressure field visualization $f = 6028\text{Hz}$, $M = 0.0$, $\mathbf{x}_{p_s} = (0\text{ m}, 0\text{ m}, 0.03\text{ m})$, flat wall (left) cavity with Kelvin cells (center) and empty cavity (right).

Figure 8: Case A - Insertion loss waterfall, $M = 0.0$, $\mathbf{x}_{ps} = (0.015\text{ m}, 0\text{ m}, 0.005\text{ m})$, comparison with flat wall (left) and empty cavity (right).

Figure 9: Case A - pressure field visualization $f = 6548\text{ Hz}$, $M = 0.2$, $\mathbf{x}_{ps} = (0.015\text{ m}, 0\text{ m}, 0.005\text{ m})$, flat wall (left) cavity with Kelvin cells (center) and empty cavity (right).

Figure 10: Case A - Insertion loss waterfall, $M = 0.2$, $\mathbf{x}_{ps} = (0.015\text{ m}, 0\text{ m}, 0.005\text{ m})$, comparison with flat wall (left) and empty cavity (right).

Figure 11: Case A - pressure field visualization $f = 6860\text{ Hz}$, $M = 0.2$, $\mathbf{x}_{ps} = (0.015\text{ m}, 0\text{ m}, 0.005\text{ m})$, flat wall (left) cavity with Kelvin cells (center) and empty cavity (right).

Figure 12: Case B - Surface averaged insertion loss vs frequency, $c_0/20a < f < c_0/5a$ (top) and $c_0/2a < f < c_0/a$ (bottom).

Figure 13: Case B - Pressure field visualisations at $f = 5\text{kHz}$ (left), $f = 40\text{kHz}$ (center) and $f = 60\text{kHz}$ (right). The mentioned band gap appears evident in the left figure.

REFERENCES

1. Lord Kelvin, Sir William Thomson, On the Division of Space with Minimum Partitional Area, *Philosophical Magazine*, 24 (151): 503 (1887), doi:10.1080/14786448708628135.
2. Yan Pennec, Jerome O. Vasseur, Bahram Djafari-Rouhani, Leonard Dobrzynski, Pierre A. Deymier Two-dimensional phononic crystals: Examples and applications, *Surface Science Report*, 65(8), 229–291, (2010)
3. Nicolas Cote, Jerome Vasseur, Quentin Souron, Anne-Christine Hladky-Hennion, Transformation of sound by a phononic crystal, *Inter-noise 2014*. (2014)